

METHODS OF FORMING THE SCIENTIFIC AWARENESS COMPETENCE OF THE DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICITY AND MAGNETISM

Usarov J.E.

Physics teacher of school № 22 of Zangiota district

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Abstract. *The formation of the competence of scientific consciousness is the basis for ensuring students' understanding of the essence of science, the connection of physical phenomena and processes, their application in life processes, and integration with other sciences. When teaching physics, it is necessary to create an optimal method for developing students' scientific thinking and expanding their terminological vocabulary. The article talks about the stages and methods of developing the competence of the scientific consciousness of the Department of Electricity and Magnetism, as well as systematic approaches to the development of basic competencies in this process, and the use of educational principles.*

Keywords: *concept, object, knowledge, scientific consciousness, competence, thinking, research, theory, methodology.*

Currently, the formation of students' scientific awareness competence is primarily focused on the development of new educational tools. Determination of the structure, content and technology of professional training in the successful implementation of design, constructive, communicative, organizational and gnostic activities of graduates of higher education and formation of professional competence of students is one of the urgent issues today. In the process of preparing students for a profession, in the process of forming their scientific awareness competence, it is necessary to take into account the following:

- in the process of professional training, it is imitated in the professional field that corresponds to the model of the graduate's personality;
- the content of future professional activities will be built on the basis of environment and person-oriented approaches, conditions will be created for the formation of professional competence of future specialists;
- reducing the time of adaptation to professional activity in the development of students' professional competence;
- development of indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of the system of preparing students for professional activity using information technology tools.

In the department of electricity and magnetism, the main attention is paid to the concept of electromagnetic fields and waves. The concept of an electromagnetic field is understood as a form of matter consisting of a sum of electric and magnetic fields that are mutually dependent and have a conditional effect on each other. A distinctive feature of the external electromagnetic field is that it affects charged particles with force, which depends on the size of the electric charge and the speed of movement of its particles. Faraday, the founder of the theory of electric and magnetic fields, explained the electromagnetic interaction of bodies based on the fact that when bodies are electrified or magnetized, there is an elastic deformation in the ether that surrounds them, and a corresponding change in tension and pressure. This space, where there are forces of interaction,

was called the electromagnetic field. A time-varying field is used in the field of telecommunications. The electric part of such a field is inseparable from the magnetic part and vice versa. However, in the theory of the electromagnetic field, starting from the time-invariant (stationary) processes, the experiments of studying electric and magnetic phenomena in nature are used, using the historical collections that have been collected until now [1].

Competences of scientific awareness of electricity and magnetism are mainly formed during the course of the lesson, and basic competencies are also developed during this formation process. Discussion of the concept of competence is one of the most important issues of pedagogy today. Hundreds of different recommended rates confirm diversity and multidimensionality.

The modern stage of economic development is associated with the concept of the "information society", in which narrow skills lose their value and are replaced by competence - in which the acquisition of a wide range of knowledge, experience and necessary personal qualities and re- transition from one field of professional activity to another with minimum time, money and effort for preparation is assumed [5].

D.McClelland's article "Testing for competence rather than for intelligence" was the first to reveal the possibilities of a competence-based approach in entrepreneurship [7]. The author emphasizes that IQ tests often do not reflect the respondent's success in real professional activities, and as an alternative to this, a competency-based approach to evaluating results should be developed.

The article "Competence: superior performance" by Spencer, L.M., & Spencer, S.M. summarizes the experience of many studies conducted in various organizations, and based on this, the authors created a dictionary of 21 competencies that describe successful employees at different levels. compiled [8]. The authors gave recommendations on the selection, training and improvement of the qualifications of the cadres, at the same time, they connected the competences to a certain person - one of their carriers.

D.McClelland, L.Spencer and S.Spencer's opinions contributed to the employers' use of new criteria in the selection of workers and specialists. Accordingly, recruitment agencies have begun to popularize the requirements of employers and methods of assessing their professional competences. This is related to qualifications, standards of professional activity, diplomas and certificates confirming that a person meets the minimum requirements to perform a certain activity. Competence has come to be seen as a collection of certain levels, ranging from the minimum, from performing the simplest tasks or solving the simplest problem, to the maximum level.

The problem of forming the competence of scientific awareness of the department of electricity and magnetism has been widely studied by modern scientists who express different points of view on this issue. N. Bogachkina, S. Skvortsova, E. Imasheva emphasized that excessive algorithmization of the educational process hinders the cognitive activity of children, and that it is successful only when the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities are implemented creatively. S. Shipovskaya, E. Tyaglova, N. Mayorova, E. Leusheva and others also dealt with this issue.

It requires the creation of the most optimal methodology for the formation of scientific awareness competencies, the development of students' scientific thinking and the expansion of their terminological vocabulary. Science is a unique form of human activity that has developed historically and has scientific facts, laws, hypotheses, theories and research methods as its result. It is important to remember that scientific awareness is often almost a denial of what seems obvious

at first glance at the everyday level. Only studies, theories, and hypotheses that require verification should be considered scientific.

It consists of two important parts:

- 1) system of scientific knowledge;
- 2) system of scientific activity.

The system of scientific knowledge consists of the following main elements:

- 1) theory;
- 2) laws and regulations;
- 3) hypotheses;
- 4) concepts;
- 5) scientific methods.

The need to form a scientific worldview comes from the fact that this process leads to the acquisition of the ability to justify all elements of knowledge and human actions based on the laws of nature, and develops the skills of action based on their behavior and in accordance with it. Therefore, the changes taking place in modern education impose significantly higher requirements on the professional preparation of future teachers, and this applies primarily to schoolchildren, students and future professionals. According to many scientists, there is a certain gap between the needs of society to attract students to the basics of scientific thinking and the inability of modern educational institutions to effectively meet these needs. This is due to the lack of development of realistic perspectives of the educational process and methodological conditions for their implementation in the formation of students' scientific awareness.

One of the most important principles of didactics is the principle of developmental education, as well as the goals of modern education, one of which is undoubtedly the formation of students' scientific awareness and thinking, mastering the methods and methods of scientific knowledge of the world, and scientific awareness in solving a number of scientific problems. should be carried out together with development.

The dialectical method also plays an important role in monitoring the competence of scientific awareness of electricity and magnetism. These dreams themselves, the development of knowledge about the objects of study, show that all knowledge not only becomes obsolete, but also has limits of application.

It is also possible to apply a systematic approach to the management of scientific awareness competence in the department of electricity and magnetism. It is used to study the general picture of the world at the macro level, and at the micro level, each element of the system is considered as a whole system in itself. The problem and issue of the approach to determining the results of development and forming the students' worldview are considered from different perspectives.

Thus, the methodology for the formation of scientific awareness competence in the department of electricity and magnetism is not always directly related to scientific research, but in any science there are important elements - laws, concepts, categories, causes, consequences, etc. The principles of openness of science and knowledge must be observed by teachers at all times and in relation to all students.

The following methods are proposed for the development of scientific awareness in students:

- 1) theoretical and practical study of the educational process;
- 2) development of dialectical thinking in the lesson;

- 3) identification of interdisciplinary relations in the process of teaching different subjects;
- 4) preparing and conducting educational activities during free time, which ensure the formation of students' scientific knowledge, views and beliefs;
- 5) involving students in various types of useful activities, contributing to the coordination of their consciousness, experiences and actions;
- 6) correcting students' wrong worldview concepts, ideas, beliefs and views. In this case, in order to form the competence of scientific awareness of the department of electricity and magnetism, students must master the methodology of scientific research.

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